

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B467
 Date: 19 July 2009
 Take Off: 08:27:49Z Basel
 Landing: 13:34:50Z Basel
 Flight Time: 5h 07m 01s

Campaign: CAVIAR
Operating Area: Jungfrauoch

POB	Position	Name	Institute	Logs y/n
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight	
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight	
3	CCM	Dawn Quinn	Directflight	
4	Mission Scientist	Chawn Harlow	Met Office	
5	Flight Manager	Jamie Trembath	FAAM	
6	Core Chem / NOx	Stephane Bauguitte	FAAM	
7	Cloud Physics	Phil Rosenberg	FAAM	
8	AVAPS	Doug Anderson	FAAM	
9	Noxy Training	Kate Turnbull	FAAM	
10	SWS	Stuart Rogers	Met Office	
11	ARIES	Dave Tiddeman	Met Office	
12	MARSS	Rob King	Met Office	
13	TAFTS	Ralph Beeby	Imperial College	Y
14	TAFTS2	Paul Green	Imperial College	
15				
16				
17				
18				
19				

Missing Log Sheet	Reason
ViRC chat log	poor comms meant no useful ViRC during CAVIAR
Core Chemistry / TDLAS	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
PSAP log	No log as PSAP pump/filter info included on Flight Summary page
CVI	No log as o operator on CAVIAR
TAFTS	No log taken?

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	03 Nov 2009	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

The following avi format video recordings should be available at the BADC in core_processed/faam-video :

faam-video-dfc_faam_20090719_r0_b467_082134_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090719_r0_b467_092344_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090719_r0_b467_102502_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20090719_r0_b467_112654_1hz.avi

faam-video-ffc_faam_20090719_r0_b467_082124_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090719_r0_b467_092123_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090719_r0_b467_092351_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090719_r0_b467_102455_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090719_r0_b467_112455_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090719_r0_b467_112641_1hz.avi

faam-video-ffc_faam_20090719_r0_b467_122641_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090719_r0_b467_122928_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20090719_r0_b467_132928_1hz.avi

faam-video-ufc_faam_20090719_r0_b467_082129_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20090719_r0_b467_092341_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20090719_r0_b467_102458_1hz.avi

faam-video-ufc_faam_20090719_r0_b467_112647_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20090719_r0_b467_122931_1hz.avi

No Digital8 video recordings were made on this flight.

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B467

Date:

Project:

Location:

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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081050		Start-Up	0.71 kft	210	
081508		ASP	0.71 kft	214	open
082749		T/O	2.7 kft	156	
082749	084153	Profile 1	3.1 - 15.0 kft	155	
084154	085049	Run 1	15.0 kft	145	
084218		Note	15.0 kft	145	Heiman cal prog 5
084305		Note	15.0 kft	145	Nev/JW Zeroed
084630		Note	15.0 kft	146	TW restarted T amb out of range
085050	085438	Profile 2	15.0 - 18.0 kft	151	
085438	090610	Run 2	18.0 kft	301	
090616	090927	Profile 3	18.0 - 21.0 kft	315	
091016	091854	Run 3	21.1 kft	157	
091855	092247	Profile 4	21.1 - 24.1 kft	155	
092248	093735	Run 4	24.1 - 24.0 kft	305	
092852		Sonde 1	24.0 kft	312	
093735	094143	Profile 5	24.0 - 28.0 kft	313	
094242	095203	Run 5	28.0 kft	157	
094310		Sonde 2	28.0 kft	147	
095631		Sonde 3	28.0 kft	311	
100352		note	28.0 kft	085	Maintain locale for sonde comms
100438	100617	Orbit 1	28.1 - 28.0 kft	028	50 degree left
100719	100920	Orbit 2	28.0 - 27.9 kft	341	45 degree left
101036	102120	Profile 6	28.0 - 16.0 kft	304	Spiral profile interupt
102456	102623	Profile 6	15.9 - 15.0 kft	216	Spiral profile restart
102714	102831	Orbit	15.1 - 15.0 kft	109	60 degree right
102859	103013	Orbit 4	15.1 kft	208	60 degree right
103937	105324	Run 6	15.1 - 15.0 kft	324	
105050		note	15.0 kft	315	Heiman cal prog 6
105324	105654	Profile 7	15.4 - 18.0 kft	355	
105655	110743	Run 7	18.0 kft	152	
111001	111211	Profile 8	18.0 - 20.0 kft	280	Profile interupt
111254	111455	Profile 8	20.0 - 22.0 kft	317	Profile restart
111456	112458	Run 8	22.0 kft	312	
112817	113030	Profile 9	22.0 - 24.0 kft	313	Profile interupt
113115	113329	Profile 9	24.0 - 26.0 kft	203	Profile restart
113329	114345	Run 9	26.0 - 26.1 kft	133	
114131		Sonde 4	26.0 kft	149	
114356	114456	Profile 10	26.0 - 27.0 kft	146	Profile interupt
114534	114839	Profile 10	27.0 - 30.1 kft	004	Profile restart
114839	120208	Run 10	30.0 kft	307	
114907		Sonde 5	30.0 kft	312	
115019		Sonde 6	30.0 kft	319	
120208	120533	Profile 11	30.3 - 32.0 kft	350	Profile interupt
120814	120917	Profile 11	32.0 - 33.0 kft	145	Profile restart/interupt
121044	121436	Profile 11	33.0 - 35.0 kft	146	Profile restart
122239	123243	Run 11.1	35.0 kft	300	
122337		Sonde 7	35.0 kft	309	
122525		Sonde 8	35.1 kft	317	
123600	124255	Run 11.2	35.0 kft	166	
124309	130527	Profile 12	35.0 - 15.0 kft	158	Spiral profile
130740	131837	Run 12	15.0 kft	296	
131542		Note	15.0 kft	316	Heiman cal prog 6
133450		Land	0.70 kft	154	13:34:50

B467 06:09:11 - 13:39:06

GLNG_PARA0581, GLAT_PARA0580

1200 NM 1000 NM 800 NM 600 NM 400 NM 200 NM 0

Sortie brief for FAAM

CAVIAR detachment 2009

Flight no:	B467
Proposed date:	Sunday 19 July 2009
Prepared by:	Chawn Harlow
Version no.:	1.0, prepared 18 July 2009 1050L (0850Z)

Aim:	To sample intensively the water vapour structure of the atmosphere above the Jungfrauoch, and measure the radiative signature of the water vapour continuum.
Airfield:	Basel
Flight location:	Swiss Alps in vicinity of Jungfrauoch high altitude research station.
Weather conditions required:	Clear sky (or very nearly clear sky, preferably $\frac{1}{8}$ cloud or less) from surface to space.
Dropsondes:	7 required. To be released from high altitudes only (FL240 and above).

Further sortie details

Coordinates: aim to fly straight and level runs between fixed coordinates

BADEP = 47° 1.6' N, 7° 25.5' E

(Jungfrauoch = 46° 32.9' N, 7° 59.1' E)

A = 46° 22.0' N, 8° 10.0' E

The runs are of approx. 10 mins duration, may be slightly longer at the lowest altitudes.

Orientation: Track approx. 142°T and reciprocal over Jungfrauoch and neighbouring glacier.

Radiometers: ARIES and TAFTS to coordinate their upward and downward views during the straight and level runs. SWS to scan a range of angles except during orbits.

Note that the following flight altitudes are examples only, and in practice these will be chosen by the mission scientist.

Sortie profile

No.	Item	Time	Cumulative time
1.	Take off from Basel at 1400Z.		
2.	Transit to arrive at BADEP at FL150	0:15	0:15
3.	Perform SLR (BADEP to A) at FL150	0:15	0:30
4.	Climbing turn to FL180, rate of climb 1000 ft/min or less.	0:05	0:35
5.	Perform SLR (A to BADEP) at FL180	0:10	0:45
6.	Climbing turn to FL210, rate of climb 1000 ft/min or less.	0:05	0:50
7.	Perform SLR (BADEP to A) at FL210	0:10	1:00
8.	Climbing turn to FL240, rate of climb 1000 ft/min or less.	0:05	1:05
9.	Perform SLR (A to BADEP) at FL240, dropping one sonde over JFJ.	0:10	1:15
10.	Climbing turn to FL280, rate of climb 1000 ft/min or less.	0:05	1:20
11.	Perform SLR (BADEP to A) at FL280, dropping two sondes (one at start, one over JFJ)	0:10	1:30
12.	Reposition from A to Jungfrauoch.	0:05	1:35
13.	Perform two orbits with maximum achievable angle of bank	0:10	1:45
14.	Perform spiral descent from FL280 to FL150 over the Jungfrauoch at 1000 ft/min.	0:15	2:00
15.	Perform two orbits with maximum achievable angle of bank	0:10	2:10
16.	Reposition from Jungfrauoch to A	0:05	2:15
17.	Perform SLR (A to BADEP) at FL150	0:15	2:30
18.	Climbing turn to FL180, rate of climb 1000 ft/min or less.	0:05	2:35
19.	Perform SLR (BADEP to A) at FL180	0:10	2:45
20.	Climbing turn to FL220, rate of climb 1000 ft/min or less.	0:05	2:50
21.	Perform SLR (A to BADEP) at FL220	0:10	3:00
22.	Climbing turn to FL260, rate of climb 1000 ft/min or less.	0:05	3:05
23.	Perform SLR (BADEP to A) at FL260, dropping one sonde	0:10	3:15
24.	Climbing turn to FL300, rate of climb 1000 ft/min or less.	0:05	3:20
25.	Perform SLR (A to BADEP) at FL300, dropping two sondes (one over glacier, one over JFJ)	0:10	3:30
26.	Climbing turn to FL350, rate of climb 1000 ft/min or less.	0:10	3:40
27.	Perform SLR (BADEP to A) at FL350, dropping one sonde over JFJ.	0:10	3:50
28.	Perform spiral descent from FL350 to FL150 over the Jungfrauoch at 1000 ft/min.	0:20	4:10
29.	Reposition from Jungfrauoch to A	0:05	4:15
30.	Perform SLR (A to BADEP) at FL150	0:15	4:30
31.	Return to Basel	0:15	4:45

B467: Sortie Debrief

Campaign: CAVIAR

Mission Scientist: Chawn Harlow

Date: 19/07/09

This sortie entailed stacked SLR's at FL150, 180, 210, 250, and 280 along the line BADEP to A. One sonde was dropped on the run at FL240 and two were dropped at FL280. The run at FL280 was followed by two orbits with an angle of bank of 45°. A spiral descent was then carried out to FL150 followed by two orbits at a 60° angle of bank. Then stacked SLR's were carried out along the line BADEP to A at FL150, 180, 220, 260, 300, and 350. One sonde was dropped at FL260, two at FL300, and two at FL350. Then a spiral descent was performed to FL 150 and a SLR from A to BADEP at FL150 on the way back to Basel.

During the first half of the flight there was a variable ~2-4 octas of Ci over the Jungfraujoch. This cleared up progressively from the south in the second half of the sortie. Some cloud was measured by the cloud physics kit near BADEP at FL300, but conditions were gin clear to the south.

All key instrumentation was operable during this sortie to my knowledge. The second sonde dropped from FL350 failed to deploy its chute. Delays were necessary at high levels due to traffic leading to late release of Sonde 3 and a prolonged climb from FL300 to FL350. The last low level run over the glacier seemed to be slightly west of the line from A to BADEP. This may mean the the glacier was missed at points in the FOV of the radiometers.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B. 467 Date 19/7/09 Name C. Harlow Page 1 of

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
0800	P1	860'	210°	Basle - Mul	8/8 Scu, on ASB pan
"	"	"	"	"	QNH 1019
082749	T/O/P1	"	155°		high rate of climb at start
"	P1	"	"		Start
	P1	4200'	"		1000'/min now
		9500'	230		Cloud ^{top} at 9500' 1/8 Ci above
084154	R1	FL150	140		Thin Ci above oper area
					2/8 Cu over OA
					No Cu over glacier
					Fresh snow on Mts.
08:54:38	R2	FL180	320		Start R2 end P2
08:50:49	R1				End P2
09:00	R2				All instruments OK
					except SID 2
090610	R2	FL180			End
090616	P3	"			Start
090927	R3 P3	FL210			Start R3 End P3
091016	R3	FL210	140		Start R3
					NOX saw dry layers at FL180
091858	R3	FL210			End R3
091855	P4				Start P4
092247	P4				End
092248	R4	FL240	320		Start R4
0926	R4				Sondes having problems w/ GPS Lock, sonde launch delayed

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B...467 Date 19/7/09 Name C. Harlow Page 2 of

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
092852	S1	FL240			Sonde 1, no GPS lock
09 20 30	R4				S1 GPS lock OK
0932	R4				CIP pitot tube US
093640					S1 on ground
					R4 extended to deal w/ wind
093735	R4	FL240			End R4
"	P5	"			Start P5
094143	P5	"			End
094242	R5	FL280	140		Start R5
094310	S2	"			Sonde 2
0952	R5				S2 on ground at 2700'
095203	R5	FL280 FL280			End R5
0950 ish	R5				S3 S3 delayed, traffic below
095629	S3	FL280	310		Sonde 3
1004 22	O1	FL280			Orbit 1 Start
100718	O2	"			Orbit 2 Start
101036	P6	FL280			Start P6 spiral
102714	O3	FL150			Orbit 3 Start
102859	O4				Orbit 4 Start
103937	R6	FL150			Run 6 Start
105324	R6	"			Run 6 end
"	P7	"			Start P7
105653	P7	FL180			End P7
"	R7	"			Start Run 7
110743	R7	"			End R7

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B...467 Date 17/7/09... Name C. Harlow... Page 3 of

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
111001	P8	FL180			Start P8
111211	P8	FL220			End P8
111456	R8	"			Start R8
112458	R8	"			End R8
112817	P9	FL220			Start P9
113329	P9	FL260			End P9
"	R9	FL260			Start R9
114131	S4	FL260			Sonde 4
1135	R9	"			In thin cloud
	R9	"			no cloud over JFK
114356	P10	FL260			Start
114345	R9	FL260			End R9
114839	P10	FL300			End P10
"	R10	"			Start R10
114907	S5	"			Sonde 5
115019	S6	"			Sonde 6
115630	R10	FL300			In cloud & sonde 6 on ground
1202	R10	FL300			End Run 10
1202	P11	FL300			Start Profile 11
1202					In Cloud
121434	P11	FL350			End Profile 11
122239	R11	FL350			Start
122337	S7	"			Sonde 7 over A
122525	S8	"			Sonde 8 over JFK
					Sonde 8 Rubbish ?

S8 shoot didn't open til 19kft.
Extra run necessary due to
ATC hold at numerous levels

Cloud Physics Flight Log B467

Date:19/07/09	Operator: PDR	DRS Time:+0	DAU1 Time:+0	DAU2 Time:+0	AUX1 Time:+0	AUX2 Time:+0
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DAU2 Disk space?

	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		CIP-100		2DC		SID2			
Operated?	Y		Y		Y		Y					
Pre-flight checks	Ref V:	4.36	Vref (>7V):	7.8	El #1:	1.65	El#1 V (>1):	2	Comms?:			
	Data TX?	y	Sample flow	1.17	El #32:	3.02	El#32 V (>1):	1.5				
			Sheath flow	13.6	El #64:	1.94						
			Spectra ok?	y	Laser current	69.9						

Just after take-off	Are SAMPLE and RECORD buttons on PADS both green?	Y	Are all heaters on? (Check ammeters and CIP dummy box heater switch).	Y
	Are all PADS instruments enabled and updating?	Y		

NOTE that CTRL+T will insert the current time where the cursor is as long as the cursor is a cursor and not a selected box.

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		CIP-100		2DC		Habit	SID2	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R			
08:28:00												Heaters on after takeoff
08:42:30												Got DAT for hotwire LWC
08:48:40												Attempt to reduce noise on SID by reducing gain to 100. No success. FIFO buffer is full, total counts > 1000 but spectrum peaks <10
08:53:00												Tries gain 150 on SID. FIFO buffer still full
08:54:00												Tried gain 50. FIFO still full but low conc on spectrum
08:55:05												Got DAT for hotwire LWC for 30 s
08:58:00												Tried gain of ten on SID, same as at 50
08:59:30												Reset gain to default level of 200. Will leave as is for duration of flight
09:11:35												Got hotwire DAT for 30 s. Dumped previous DAT ~1 min earlier as we were not quite level
09:24:00												Got hotwire DAT term for 30 s
09:30:00												CIP pitot frozen, set TAS to manual on pads at 100 m/s
09:43:30												Got DAT for hotwire for 30 s

GMT	Height	CDP		PCASP SPP-200		CIP-100		2DC		Habit	SID2	Comments
		#/cc	MVD	#/cc	MVD	#/cc	Mean R	#/L	Max R			
11:06:30												Got DAT for hotwire for 30 s
12:23:10												Got DAT for hotwire for 30 s
12:37:00												Got DAT for hotwire for 30 s
13:08:00												Got DAT for hotwire for 30 s

Post flight

Instrument	Diagnostics		Brief report on instrument performance
PCASP (old)	Vref:		
	Flow:		
2DC	El#1:	1.8	Worked as expected
	El#32:	1.3	
PCASP SPP-200	Ref V:	7.6	Worked well v little ch1 noise
	Flow:		
CDP	Laser V:	4.1	Worked as expected
FFSSP	Ref V:		
SID 3	Laser V:		
Rack Equipment			Please note SEADAS disk space remaining.

FAAM Dropsonde Flight Log

Flight No.	B467	Date	19/07/2009	Operator	Doug Anderson	Page No.	1 of 1
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GMT	Sonde No.	Event <i>eg land, splashdown</i>	Comments <i>pressure hPa, T deg C, RH %, wind direction deg, wind speed m/s, longitude, latitude, height m</i>
09:28:57	1	Launch	392.40 -26.10 25.34 277.50 37.40 0.80 7.806900 46.701600 7320.30
09:36:31	1	Land	870.18 9.98 72.04 249.26 2.97 -9.70 7.898365 46.698456 1219.69
			End drop time override 455.1. Surface parameter 870.2Mb. Surface alt unknown ticked <i>GPS took approx 1 min to lock in after launch - it hadn't locked in the cabin before launch</i> D20090719_092856.1 AVAPS-T01 STA 082119311 090719 092047.00
09:43:15	2	Launch	328.50 -37.00 77.47 281.40 30.90 1.00 7.443000 47.005500 8550.20
09:52:23	2	Land	939.59 13.35 78.16 269.79 2.63 -11.36 7.572439 47.009684 498.83
			No end drop time override. Surface alt unknown ticked D20090719_094314.2 AVAPS-T02 LAU 082149328 090719 094314.53
09:56:36	3	Launch	328.70 -36.60 67.06 269.40 37.40 0.90 8.127200 46.425000 8546.30
10:03:42	3	Land	766.77 3.18 75.55 320.60 0.22 -11.20 8.238371 46.412141 2144.17
			End drop time override 428.4. Surface parameter 766.8Mb. Surface alt unknown ticked D20090719_095634.3 AVAPS-T03 LAU 081939313 090719 095634.53
11:41:36	4	Launch	359.60 -31.60 63.73 279.60 26.90 0.50 7.991400 46.542600 7930.90
11:46:34	4	Land	608.44 -10.03 95.47 222.53 4.28 -12.76 8.072864 46.538038 3558.48
			End drop time override 297.7. Surface parameter 643.8Mb. Surface alt unknown ticked. May have fallen down cliff face towards end. D20090719_114136.1 AVAPS-T01 LAU 082149499 090719 114136.00
11:49:12	5	Launch	300.20 -42.00 77.31 272.10 37.90 -0.30 8.061000 46.466800 9159.80
11:56:44	5	Land	734.64 1.22 96.20 328.60 0.31 -10.19 8.181764 46.454898 2477.08
			End drop time override. Surface parameter Mb. Surface alt unknown ticked D20090719_114910.2 AVAPS-T02 LAU 082119246 090719 114910.78
11:50:24	6	Launch	300.50 -42.10 87.04 274.20 38.50 0.50 7.977900 46.554200 9152.50
11:56:36	6	Land	661.27 -4.32 69.20 103.99 3.98 -13.82 8.093492 46.539538 3330.49
			End drop time override 370.0. Surface parameter 661.3Mb. Surface alt unknown ticked D20090719_115022.3 AVAPS-T03 LAU 081939379 090719 115022.76
12:25:27	7	Launch	237.80 -52.60 48.73 278.20 41.40 0.40 7.983700 46.553600 10683.80
12:32:56	7	Land	653.78 -5.80 87.77 109.34 1.85 -11.70 8.130183 46.538848 3408.05
			End drop time override. Surface parameter Mb. Surface alt unknown ticked D20090719_122528.1 AVAPS-T01 LAU 082029207 090719 122528.30
12:23:39	8	Launch	237.90 -51.60 46.72 277.50 39.10 -0.10 8.115600 46.424700 10681.40
12:31:49	8	Land	700.33 -1.61 96.03 238.25 6.09 -12.23 8.270284 46.412196 2922.31
			End drop time override 489.7. Surface parameter 700.3Mb. Surface alt unknown ticked. Set Heights missing ticked <i>Seems to have fallen very fast so probably not properly opened parachute - data only coming in at approx 18000ft. Overtook sonde dropped 2 mins earlier and landed first too. Launched last but landed earlier than seventh sonde.</i> D20090719_122340.4 AVAPS-T04 LAU 082149379 090719 122340.11

Flight:

B467

KEY

 Not Fitted

 Fitted, Not Operated

 Duff Data

 Minor Problems

 OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:

Heimann:

Deiced Temp:

Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:

Buck CR2:

General Eastern:

Johnson Williams:

Nevzorov:

Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:

Forward Facing:

Rearward Facing:

Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:

GIN Applanix:

INU Honeywell:

Radar Altimeter:

RVSM IAS:

RVSM Static Pressure:

XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

HORACE:

AMTG:

AVAPS:

Cabin Pressure:

Printer:

S9 Static Pressure:

Satcom C:

Satcom H (VIRC):

Turb Centre-Static:

Turb Left Right:

Turb Up-Down:

Turb Horizontal Chk:

Turb Vertical Chk:

Weather Radar:

DLUs:

DLU AERACK:

DLU BBR Lower:

DLU BBR Upper:

DLU Core Chem:

DLU Core Consoles:

DLU Port Aft:

DLU Port Fwd:

DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:

BBR (clear) Lower:

BBR (IR) Lower:

BBR (red) Lower:

Upper:

BBR (clear) Upper:

BBR (IR) Upper:

BBR (red) Upper:

ARIES:

DEIMOS:

IR Camera:

JNO2 Lower:

JNO2 Upper:

JO1D Lower:

JO1D Upper:

MARSS:

SHIMS Lower:

SHIMS Upper:

SWS:

TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

2DC:

2DP:

FFSSP:

PCASP:

PCASP SPP-200:

2DS:

ADA:

CAPS:

CCN:

CDP (fuselage):

CDP (Canister):

CIP 100 (PIP):

CIP 25 (CIP):

CPI:

CVI (Inlet):

CVI PCASP-X:

CVI Ly-A Hygro:

FSSP (UMan):

SID1:

SID2:

SID3:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:

CPC 3786 H2O:

Filters 47mm:

Filters 90mm:

Neph - Dry:

Neph - Wet:

PSAP:

AMS:

CPC (AMS):

SMPS (AMS):

CPC 3010A (CVI):

INC:

Mini-LIDAR:

SP2:

UHSAS:

VACC:

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:

NOx TE42C:

Ozone TE49C:

Ozone TE49:

SO2 TE43C:

TDLAS (NIR) CH4:

TDLAS (NIR) CO2:

FAGE:

Formaldehyde:

NOx FAAM:

NOxy:

ORAC:

PAN:

PERCA:

Peroxide:

PTRMS:

TDLAS (1C):

WAS Bags:

WAS Bottles:

Misc Non-Core

CASI/ATM:

LIDAR (big):

LTI:

SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B466

Date: 16/7/09

Instruments

1. Appears that there is some condensation on Heiman Lens.
2. RFC not operational
3. Satcom failed at 8.50 when we came over the mountains
4. 9.22 camera recording failed again and happened every hour

Aircraft

- 1.
- 2.
- 3.

Satcom-H Calls

nil

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) $\frac{1}{4}$ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

Pre-Flighter's Log

Date: 19/7/09

Flight No: B467

Pre-Flighter: *Amw*

No.	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
1	☒	Hangar	Collect spanners	Core Chem - 9/16" & 11/16"
Aircraft Cabin: Power-up				
2	☒	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	
3	☒	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	☒	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	
5	☒	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	
6	☒	Aft CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
7	☒	Fore CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
8	☒	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
9	☒	HORACE	Recording data	
10	☒	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
11	☒	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
12	☒	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
13	☒	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	
14	☒	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	<i>RED CAM INOP.</i>
15	☒	Video Laptop	Checked onboard	
16	☒	FWVS	Set up & check on AUTO	<i>DAVE T</i>
17	☒	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked then OFF	
18	☒	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
19	☒	TWC	Fitted & signals checked	
20	☒	GE	Balance checked then back to DP	
21	☒	GPS (XR5M)	Checked	
22	☒	Satcom C	Checked	
23	☒	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	In cockpit
24	☒	CNC	Butanol fitted	<i>WATER DRAIN DOWN</i>
25	☒	Dry Neph	Power up & Zero Cal	
26	☒	PSAP	Pre-flight log actions complete	
27	☒	CGPS	CBs and PC ON	
28	☒	3786 CPC	DI Checked / Topped up	

No.	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
29	☒	CCN Water	Supply filled / Drain empty	
30	☒	CCN SS cols A & B	Set to manual A0.2, B0.1	
31	☒	CCN Pressure	Normally set to 650mb	
32	☒	CCN Flow Ratios	A & B = 10 ± 0.3	
33	☒	3786 CPC	Drained	
34	☒	CPC Laptop	AIM Software set up	
External Checks				
35	☒	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
36	☒	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
37	☒	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
38	☒	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
39	☒	Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
40	☒	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
41	☒	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
42	☒	WAS Bottles	No. fitted and position.	
43	☒	Camera Windows	Cleaned	<i>RFC INOP</i>
44	☒	Heimann	Lens checked OK	<i>WATER ON LENS</i>
45	☒	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
46	☒	All other covers	Removed	
47	☒	Pre-flight Bag	Returned to hold	** Check no butanol**
48	☒	Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
49	☒	Tools	Avalon informed	
50	☐			
Avalon Checks				
51	☒	Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		<u>Signed</u>
52	☒	ICEX applied		
53	☒	Turb Probe - Traps emptied, detail contents -		a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) 1/4 full or more

ARIES flight log

Flight: 13467

page 1 of 2

Date: 19/7/09

Operator(s): D. TIDDEMAN

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: CAUIAK SWITZERLAND

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
							CNZ
							Cursor Nadir Zenith 30s (CH 30s, N 30s, 2 30s) repeat
							Cohered up to time
0845							Set 1 hour wrong... lost comms with Restart software instrument
085009	FL150	CNZ		0	71	31	
085150	probe						Stop script
085440	FL180	CNZ		0	71	31	
090645	"	CNZ		0	71	30	8 Stopped
090935	FL210	CNZ		0	71	30	
091954	FL210	CNZ		0	71	31	Stopped
092245	FL240	CNZ		0	71	31	
093735	"	"		"	71	30	Stopped
094147	FL280	CNZ		0	71	31	Start
095200	FL280	CNZ		0	71	31	Stopped
095630	FL280	CNZ		0	71	31	Start
095925	FL280	CNZ		0	70	30	Stop
103440	FL150	CNZ		0	71	31	
103530	"						Stop (turn)
103939	FL150	CNZ		0	71	31	Started
105400	FL150	CNZ		0	71	31	Stopped
105700	FL180	CNZ		0	71	30	Start
110744	FL180	CNZ		0	71	30	Stop
111502	FL220	CNZ		0	71	31	Start
112503	FL220	CNZ		0	71	30	stop
113340	FL260	CNZ		0	71	31	Start
114410	FL260	CNZ		0	70	31	Stop
114900	FL300	CNZ		0	71	31	Start
120215	FL300	CNZ		0	70	31	Stop

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	19/07/09	Flight	B467	log pages
Operator(s)	Rob King		Campaign	CAVIAR		
Departure			Arrival			

System start

MARSS

Visual pod inspection						•
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers						•
Close all MARSS circuit breakers						•
FERA on					at time	0700
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	°C	Ch	°C	Ch18	°C
Temperature controller set points		54°C	17	58°C	-20	40°C
MARSS CPU on					at time	0700
Initial target temperatures	Hot	294	Cold	287		
Target heating						•
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						•
Scanning on (LMD box)					at time	
Scan indication	Monitor			•	Visual	

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers						
Turn on Deimos CPU						
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						
Start Deimos Software					at time	
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold			
Target heating						
Scan indication	Monitor			•	Visual	
Weather	Cloud		Precip			
	Surface		Pressure			
	Other					

System functionality check

(after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC} = t_{DRS} +$	0	at time		
Brightness temps 'sensible'					•
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot	Cold		
	Deimos:	Hot	Cold		
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B	
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)	
	Ch16	Ch17	Ch18	Ch19	Ch20
	(40-44)	(45-49)	(40-44)	(40-44)	(44-48)

Power changeover

Headset on before start						•
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.					•
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)						•
Exit Deimos Software (x)						
POWER CHANGEOVER						
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton					•
Restart Deimos Software						
System running again					at time	
					0913	

B467_SWS_SHIMS_EventLog

```

06:21:02.15 --- - - -
06:21:02.15 --- - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
06:21:02.15 --- - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
06:21:02.15 --- - - - +++ Flight no. B467
06:21:02.15 --- - - -
06:21:19.43 --- - - - *** Operator: Stuart Rogers
06:21:35.09 SWS - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
06:21:37.72 USH - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
06:21:40.04 LSH - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
06:21:52.73 LSH - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
06:21:52.74 USH - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
06:21:52.75 SWS - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
06:21:56.88 --- - - - Reset shutters.
06:22:08.85 SWS - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
06:22:13.47 SWS - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
06:22:18.00 USH - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
06:22:21.93 USH - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
06:22:26.21 LSH - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
06:22:30.62 LSH - - - 100 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
06:22:52.06 SWS - - - ERROR: Failed to initialise telescope.
06:22:59.12 SWS - - - Telescope disabled.
06:23:07.55 SWS - - - Telescope motor initialised.
06:23:17.49 SWS 0.0 - - - Telescope sent to 174.000
06:23:19.15 SWS 173.5 - - - Telescope stopped.
06:23:29.37 SWS 174.0 - - - Telescope sent to 0.000
06:23:31.03 SWS 0.6 - - - Telescope stopped.
06:23:55.25 SWS - - - Telescope disabled.
08:04:51.24 SWS - - - Telescope motor initialised.
08:05:48.10 SWS 0.0 - - - Telescope sent to 113.177
08:05:49.23 SWS 111.1 - - - Telescope stopped.
08:06:06.74 SWS - - 50 - VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
08:06:09.91 --- - - - Reset shutters.
08:08:45.46 SWS - 100 - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
08:08:48.38 USH - 100 - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
08:08:51.42 LSH - 100 - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
08:13:01.53 LSH - 250 - Sample period changed from 100ms to 250ms.
08:13:05.58 USH - 250 - Sample period changed from 100ms to 250ms.
08:13:08.80 SWS - 250 - Sample period changed from 100ms to 250ms.
08:13:26.42 --- - - - Reset shutters.
08:13:33.99 LSH - - - Dark measurement started.
08:13:34.01 USH - - - Dark measurement started.
08:13:34.03 SWS - - - Dark measurement started.
08:13:35.43 LSH - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:13:35.62 USH - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:13:35.83 SWS - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:13:44.76 SWS - - - Dark measurement started.
08:13:44.98 LSH - - - Dark measurement started.
08:13:45.19 USH - - - Dark measurement started.
08:13:46.23 SWS - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:13:46.42 LSH - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:13:46.65 USH - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:13:57.42 USH - - 303 0 Manual scene recording started.
08:14:00.32 LSH - - 303 0 Manual scene recording started.
08:15:07.75 --- - - - *** Taxiing
08:20:01.26 SWS 113.2 - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
08:20:02.40 SWS -0.6 - - - Telescope stopped.
08:20:07.85 SWS - - 30 - VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 30ms.
08:20:13.53 SWS - - - Dark measurement started.
08:20:14.97 SWS - - - Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:20:17.70 SWS - - 303 0 Manual scene recording started.
08:28:46.11 --- - - - *** T/O 0827--ish
08:29:45.50 SWS - - - Dark measurement started.
08:29:45.70 USH - - - Dark measurement started.
08:29:45.71 LSH - - - Dark measurement started.
08:29:46.97 SWS - - 303 0 Manual scene recording started.
08:29:47.21 USH - - 303 0 Manual scene recording started.

```

08:29:47.36	LSH	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
08:33:47.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
08:33:52.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
08:34:04.03	USH	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
08:34:06.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:34:08.00	USH	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
08:35:26.87	---	-	-	-	-	*** Incorrect reporting of int times on scene recording
08:36:20.94	SWS	-	100	-	-	Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
08:36:23.51	USH	-	100	-	-	Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
08:36:26.14	LSH	-	100	-	-	Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
08:42:02.01	---	-	-	-	-	*** FL150
08:43:42.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:43:46.71	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 30ms to 50ms.
08:43:50.62	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 100ms.
08:43:54.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:43:54.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
08:43:55.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:43:59.58	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
08:44:03.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:44:05.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
08:44:07.48	SWS	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
08:44:17.21	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
08:44:17.63	SWS	-4.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -55.000
08:44:31.73	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
08:44:37.25	SWS	7.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
08:44:46.69	SWS	7.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -55.000
08:44:57.31	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
08:45:15.95	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
08:45:25.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:45:27.29	USH	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
08:45:28.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:45:29.96	LSH	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
08:45:34.66	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
08:45:53.37	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
08:46:12.12	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
08:46:30.86	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
08:46:49.64	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
08:47:08.38	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
08:47:27.19	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
08:47:45.94	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
08:48:04.50	SWS	-54.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
08:48:23.27	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
08:48:42.00	SWS	-55.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
08:49:00.82	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
08:49:19.51	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
08:49:38.21	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
08:49:56.99	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
08:50:15.71	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
08:50:34.51	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
08:50:53.38	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
08:51:12.00	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
08:51:30.74	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
08:51:49.62	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
08:52:08.38	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
08:52:27.05	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
08:52:45.72	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
08:53:04.46	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
08:53:17.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
08:53:23.18	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
08:53:25.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
08:53:41.84	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
08:54:00.50	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
08:54:19.22	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
08:54:31.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
08:54:38.00	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
08:54:56.65	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
08:55:09.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
08:55:09.87	---	-	-	-	-	*** FL180

08:55:15.40	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
08:55:18.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
08:55:21.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:55:21.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
08:55:22.57	SWS	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
08:55:25.40	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
08:55:28.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:55:30.23	SWS	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
08:55:34.24	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
08:55:36.95	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
08:55:38.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
08:55:40.43	SWS	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
08:55:53.07	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
08:56:11.77	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
08:56:30.56	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
08:56:49.41	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
08:56:57.42	---	-	-	-	-	*** SWS glint off tail?
08:57:08.32	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
08:57:27.07	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
08:57:45.90	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
08:58:04.63	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
08:58:23.44	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
08:58:42.35	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
08:59:01.10	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
08:59:19.82	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
08:59:38.55	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
08:59:57.38	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:00:16.19	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:00:35.04	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:00:53.83	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:01:12.57	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:01:22.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:01:22.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:01:22.93	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:01:24.32	SWS	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
09:01:24.51	USH	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
09:01:24.76	LSH	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
09:01:31.28	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:01:50.16	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:02:08.87	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:02:27.74	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:02:46.62	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:03:05.37	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:03:24.10	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:03:43.03	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:04:01.88	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:04:20.74	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:04:39.62	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:04:58.52	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:05:17.26	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:05:36.11	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:05:54.85	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:06:13.64	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:06:14.80	---	-	-	-	-	*** 8/8 cloud below
09:06:32.44	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:06:36.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:06:51.24	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:07:10.21	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:07:29.10	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:07:31.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:07:47.89	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:08:06.80	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:08:25.62	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:08:44.49	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:09:03.37	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:09:22.23	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:09:29.74	---	-	-	-	-	*** FL210
09:09:40.85	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:09:59.40	SWS	-54.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0

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09:10:18.22 SWS 55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:10:36.99 SWS -55.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:10:55.76 SWS 55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:11:14.74 SWS -55.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:11:33.71 SWS 55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:11:52.54 SWS -55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:12:11.49 SWS 55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:12:30.27 SWS -55.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:12:49.05 SWS 55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:13:07.95 SWS -55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:13:26.77 SWS 55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:13:45.71 SWS -55.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:14:04.49 SWS 55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:14:23.43 SWS -55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:14:42.29 SWS 55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:15:01.18 SWS -55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:15:20.07 SWS 55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:15:39.01 SWS -55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:15:57.77 SWS 55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:16:16.81 SWS -55.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:16:27.30 USH - - - Dark measurement started.
09:16:27.33 LSH - - - Dark measurement started.
09:16:27.41 SWS - - - Dark measurement started.
09:16:28.81 USH - - 303 0 Manual scene recording started.
09:16:28.98 LSH - - 303 0 Manual scene recording started.
09:16:29.20 SWS - - 303 0 Manual scene recording started.
09:16:35.72 SWS 55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:16:54.69 SWS -55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:17:13.58 SWS 55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:17:32.62 SWS -55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:17:51.53 SWS 55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:17:53.56 --- - - - *** Probably not tail glint earlier?
09:18:10.46 SWS -55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:18:29.38 SWS 55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:18:48.28 SWS -55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:19:07.06 SWS 55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:19:26.02 SWS -55.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:19:44.74 SWS 55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:20:03.59 SWS -55.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:20:22.50 SWS 55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:20:41.38 SWS -55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:21:00.31 SWS 55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:21:19.28 SWS -55.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:21:38.21 SWS 55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:21:57.17 SWS -55.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:22:16.21 SWS 55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:22:35.29 SWS -55.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:22:47.98 SWS - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:22:54.24 SWS 55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:22:56.95 SWS - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:23:11.07 --- - - - *** FL240
09:23:13.19 SWS -55.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:23:26.49 SWS - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:23:32.05 SWS 55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:23:35.81 SWS - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:23:40.85 SWS - - - Dark measurement started.
09:23:42.31 SWS - - 303 0 Manual scene recording started.
09:23:45.98 SWS - - 30 - VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 30ms.
09:23:47.71 SWS - - - Dark measurement started.
09:23:49.33 SWS - - 303 0 Manual scene recording started.
09:23:51.03 SWS -55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:24:10.02 SWS 55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:24:28.93 SWS -55.1 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:24:47.88 SWS 55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:25:06.82 SWS -55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:25:25.78 SWS 55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:25:27.26 --- - - - *** 'Glint' is Ci forward-scatter?
09:25:44.73 SWS -55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:26:03.75 SWS 55.0 - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0

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09:26:22.71	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:26:41.68	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:26:46.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:27:00.61	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:27:14.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:27:19.51	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:27:23.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:27:31.79	SWS	-	-	20	-	VIS int.time changed from 30ms to 20ms.
09:27:33.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:27:34.67	SWS	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
09:27:37.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:27:38.04	SWS	-54.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:27:39.47	USH	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
09:27:40.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:27:41.71	LSH	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
09:27:56.91	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:28:15.89	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:28:34.80	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:28:47.77	---	-	-	-	-	*** Some Ci (+contrails?) above
09:28:53.79	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:29:12.61	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:29:17.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:29:31.55	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:29:50.49	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:30:09.45	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:30:23.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:30:28.38	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:30:47.35	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:31:01.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:31:06.21	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:31:10.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:31:25.09	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:31:39.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:31:44.05	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:31:48.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:32:03.03	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:32:22.06	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:32:41.08	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:32:59.99	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:33:18.94	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:33:33.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:33:38.00	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:33:41.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:33:56.93	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:34:15.95	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:34:35.00	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:34:54.05	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:35:13.04	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:35:27.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:35:31.92	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:35:35.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:35:50.94	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:36:05.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:36:09.95	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:36:13.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:36:29.00	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:36:47.55	SWS	54.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:37:06.46	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:37:20.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:37:25.38	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:37:29.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:37:44.43	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:38:03.47	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:38:09.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:38:22.37	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:38:41.43	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:39:00.49	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:39:19.03	SWS	54.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:39:37.58	SWS	-54.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0

09:39:56.49	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:40:15.01	SWS	-54.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:40:33.97	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:40:52.91	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:41:11.98	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:41:30.96	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:41:49.56	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:41:55.28	---	-	-	-	-	*** FL280
09:42:08.59	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:42:27.55	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:42:43.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:42:46.55	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:42:48.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:42:54.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:42:54.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:42:54.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:42:55.61	USH	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
09:42:55.79	LSH	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
09:42:55.90	SWS	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
09:42:55.94	USH	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
09:43:05.09	SWS	54.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:43:23.63	SWS	-54.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:43:42.16	SWS	54.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:44:01.14	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:44:20.22	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:44:38.76	SWS	-54.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:44:57.80	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:45:14.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:45:16.88	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:45:18.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:45:35.96	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:45:53.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
09:45:54.93	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:46:13.97	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:46:32.54	SWS	-54.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:46:51.59	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:47:10.66	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:47:29.28	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:47:48.35	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:48:07.39	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:48:26.41	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:48:45.46	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
09:49:04.07	SWS	-54.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
09:49:14.26	SWS	4.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
09:49:18.52	SWS	3.9	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
09:49:20.28	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
09:58:00.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:58:00.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:58:00.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:58:02.12	SWS	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
09:58:02.29	LSH	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
09:58:02.51	USH	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
10:04:21.47	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
10:04:23.24	SWS	-6.1	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:04:25.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:04:26.63	SWS	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
10:04:31.19	SWS	-	-	10	-	VIS int.time changed from 20ms to 10ms.
10:04:32.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:04:34.90	SWS	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
10:04:44.58	---	-	-	-	-	*** Orbit
10:06:22.33	SWS	-	-	20	-	VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 20ms.
10:06:27.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:06:29.30	SWS	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
10:07:21.67	---	-	-	-	-	*** Orbit 45deg
10:09:23.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:09:25.06	SWS	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
10:09:30.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:09:32.53	USH	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
10:09:32.88	USH	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.

10:09:34.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:09:35.87	LSH	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
10:10:47.64	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 20ms to 50ms.
10:10:51.53	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 100ms.
10:10:53.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:10:54.89	SWS	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
10:11:20.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:11:47.06	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
10:11:56.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:11:58.38	SWS	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
10:12:07.94	---	-	-	-	-	*** Spiral descent
10:13:16.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:20:18.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:20:19.98	SWS	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
10:20:27.69	SWS	-	-	10	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 10ms.
10:20:31.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:20:32.59	SWS	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
10:23:44.92	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 50ms.
10:23:48.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:23:49.93	SWS	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
10:24:34.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:24:51.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:24:52.52	USH	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
10:24:53.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:24:54.67	LSH	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
10:26:56.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:28:35.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:28:37.11	SWS	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
10:28:41.09	SWS	-	-	10	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 10ms.
10:28:43.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:28:45.32	SWS	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
10:30:15.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:30:17.42	SWS	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
10:30:46.48	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 50ms.
10:30:48.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:30:49.80	SWS	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
10:31:44.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:32:07.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:37:41.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:38:16.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:38:16.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:38:16.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:38:18.11	LSH	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
10:38:18.33	USH	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
10:38:18.55	SWS	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
10:38:24.10	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
10:38:25.86	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:39:46.59	---	-	-	-	-	*** FL150
10:40:52.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:41:24.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:41:25.87	SWS	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
10:41:30.28	SWS	-	-	30	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 30ms.
10:41:35.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:41:37.38	SWS	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
10:41:41.04	SWS	-	-	15	-	VIS int.time changed from 30ms to 15ms.
10:41:44.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:41:45.83	SWS	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
10:42:50.25	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
10:42:51.96	SWS	-5.6	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:42:57.02	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
10:42:57.45	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -55.000
10:43:07.37	SWS	54.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
10:43:08.07	SWS	51.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
10:43:08.81	SWS	46.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
10:43:09.57	SWS	42.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
10:43:10.32	SWS	38.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
10:43:11.04	SWS	33.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
10:43:11.76	SWS	29.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
10:43:12.50	SWS	24.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0

10:43:13.24	SWS	20.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
10:43:13.98	SWS	16.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
10:43:14.72	SWS	11.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
10:43:15.44	SWS	7.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
10:43:16.18	SWS	2.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
10:43:16.94	SWS	-1.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
10:43:17.68	SWS	-6.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
10:43:18.43	SWS	-10.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
10:43:19.17	SWS	-15.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
10:43:19.92	SWS	-19.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
10:43:20.67	SWS	-24.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
10:43:21.41	SWS	-28.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
10:43:22.15	SWS	-33.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
10:43:22.92	SWS	-37.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
10:43:23.67	SWS	-42.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
10:43:24.40	SWS	-46.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
10:43:25.15	SWS	-50.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
10:43:25.91	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
10:43:44.65	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
10:44:03.30	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
10:44:22.06	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
10:44:40.84	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
10:44:59.45	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
10:45:18.15	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
10:45:36.84	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
10:45:55.62	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
10:46:14.31	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
10:46:33.10	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
10:46:51.81	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
10:47:10.66	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
10:47:29.50	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
10:47:48.19	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
10:48:06.90	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
10:48:25.58	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
10:48:44.32	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
10:49:03.05	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
10:49:21.82	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
10:49:40.46	SWS	-54.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
10:49:59.15	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
10:50:17.83	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
10:50:36.57	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
10:50:55.30	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
10:51:14.00	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
10:51:32.78	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
10:51:51.58	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
10:52:10.35	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
10:52:29.23	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
10:52:48.01	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
10:53:06.73	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
10:53:25.58	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
10:53:36.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:53:36.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:53:36.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:53:37.62	SWS	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
10:53:37.83	LSH	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
10:53:38.13	USH	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
10:53:44.39	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
10:54:03.14	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
10:54:11.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:54:21.99	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
10:54:33.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:54:40.83	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
10:54:44.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:54:59.58	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
10:55:18.41	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
10:55:37.18	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
10:55:55.98	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
10:56:00.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
10:56:14.93	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0

10:56:33.75	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
10:56:52.57	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
10:57:11.33	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
10:57:30.22	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
10:57:41.29	---	-	-	-	-	*** FL180
10:57:49.02	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
10:58:07.83	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
10:58:26.60	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
10:58:45.60	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
10:59:04.31	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
10:59:23.06	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
10:59:41.83	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:00:00.69	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:00:19.47	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:00:38.33	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:00:57.14	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:01:15.96	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:01:34.87	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:01:53.68	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:02:12.52	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:02:31.25	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:02:50.00	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:03:08.83	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:03:27.68	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:03:46.59	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:04:05.32	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:04:24.20	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:04:43.05	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:05:02.00	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:05:16.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:05:20.77	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:05:24.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:05:39.66	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:05:54.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:05:58.42	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:06:01.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:06:17.33	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:06:31.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:06:35.95	SWS	-54.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:06:39.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:06:54.86	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:07:13.77	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:07:17.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:07:32.73	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:07:51.53	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:08:10.28	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:08:16.06	SWS	22.6	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:08:20.39	SWS	22.6	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
11:08:22.07	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:08:27.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:08:27.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:08:27.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:08:29.36	LSH	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
11:08:29.54	USH	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
11:08:29.86	SWS	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
11:08:38.71	SWS	-	-	30	-	VIS int.time changed from 15ms to 30ms.
11:08:42.54	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 30ms to 50ms.
11:08:44.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:08:45.63	SWS	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
11:09:16.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:09:35.78	SWS	-	-	30	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 30ms.
11:09:37.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:09:39.38	SWS	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
11:12:22.03	---	-	-	-	-	*** FL200
11:14:56.79	---	-	-	-	-	*** FL220
11:15:03.07	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
11:15:04.86	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:15:10.06	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:15:10.50	SWS	-4.9	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -55.000

11:15:20.98	SWS	52.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:15:21.69	SWS	48.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:15:22.44	SWS	43.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:15:23.19	SWS	39.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:15:23.97	SWS	34.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:15:24.72	SWS	29.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:15:25.43	SWS	25.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:15:26.17	SWS	21.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:15:26.92	SWS	16.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:15:27.67	SWS	12.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:15:28.47	SWS	7.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:15:29.22	SWS	2.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:15:29.98	SWS	-1.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:15:30.73	SWS	-6.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:15:31.45	SWS	-10.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:15:32.21	SWS	-15.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:15:32.98	SWS	-19.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:15:33.73	SWS	-24.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:15:34.45	SWS	-28.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:15:35.17	SWS	-32.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:15:35.97	SWS	-37.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:15:36.72	SWS	-42.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:15:37.44	SWS	-46.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:15:38.18	SWS	-50.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:15:38.92	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:15:57.87	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:16:16.83	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:16:35.76	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:16:54.76	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:17:13.89	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:17:32.80	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:17:51.73	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:18:10.68	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:18:29.61	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:18:48.55	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:19:07.58	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:19:26.49	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:19:45.37	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:20:04.33	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:20:23.21	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:20:42.06	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:21:00.98	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:21:19.89	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:21:38.79	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:21:58.32	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:22:17.16	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:22:36.09	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:22:54.96	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:23:13.87	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:23:32.67	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:23:51.44	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:24:10.27	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:24:29.39	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:24:48.48	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:25:07.37	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:25:26.36	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:25:43.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:25:43.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:25:43.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:25:45.14	SWS	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
11:25:45.41	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:25:45.63	USH	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
11:25:45.74	LSH	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
11:26:04.21	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:26:22.93	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:26:41.79	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:27:00.62	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:27:19.46	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:27:38.41	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0

11:27:57.31	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:28:16.21	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:28:35.12	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:28:53.82	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:29:12.88	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:29:19.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:29:31.79	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:29:39.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:29:50.89	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:30:01.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:30:09.87	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:30:14.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:30:28.63	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:30:47.51	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:31:06.26	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:31:25.17	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:31:43.99	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:32:02.87	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:32:21.90	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:32:40.88	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:32:59.99	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:33:19.01	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:33:38.06	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:33:50.07	---	-	-	-	-	*** FL260
11:33:56.88	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:34:15.89	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:34:34.78	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:34:53.82	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:35:12.82	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:35:31.91	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:35:50.89	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:36:09.92	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:36:28.82	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:36:47.81	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:37:06.69	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:37:25.59	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:37:44.60	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:38:03.58	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:38:22.59	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:38:41.50	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:39:00.59	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:39:19.44	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:39:38.50	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:39:57.48	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:40:16.43	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:40:35.48	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:40:54.46	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:41:13.51	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:41:32.53	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:41:51.60	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:42:02.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:42:02.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:42:02.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:42:03.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:42:03.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:42:04.18	SWS	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
11:42:04.98	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:42:05.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:42:10.64	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:42:10.80	USH	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
11:42:13.11	LSH	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
11:42:29.63	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:42:48.57	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:43:07.50	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:43:26.48	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:43:45.50	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:44:04.41	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:44:23.39	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:44:42.45	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0

11:45:01.37	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:45:20.27	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:45:39.34	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:45:58.38	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:46:09.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:46:16.94	SWS	54.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:46:25.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:46:35.99	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:46:43.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:46:54.51	SWS	54.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:47:06.29	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:47:13.51	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:47:17.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:47:32.51	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:47:51.47	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:48:10.44	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:48:29.39	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:48:48.38	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:48:48.59	---	-	-	-	-	*** FL300
11:49:07.34	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:49:26.28	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:49:45.31	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:50:04.33	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:50:23.34	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:50:42.40	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:51:01.42	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:51:20.51	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:51:39.55	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:51:58.66	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:52:17.73	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:52:36.77	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:52:55.71	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:53:14.76	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:53:26.73	---	-	-	-	-	*** Lost LSH NIR
11:53:32.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:53:33.87	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:53:39.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Instrument closed.
11:53:41.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
11:53:45.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene sampling started - Not Recording!
11:53:48.27	LSH	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
11:53:52.84	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:54:02.59	---	-	-	-	-	*** LSH NIR is back
11:54:11.46	SWS	-54.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:54:17.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:54:18.98	LSH	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
11:54:23.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:54:25.35	USH	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
11:54:28.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:54:29.52	SWS	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
11:54:30.07	SWS	54.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:54:48.60	SWS	-54.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:55:07.39	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:55:26.29	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:55:44.96	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:56:03.55	SWS	-54.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:56:22.32	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:56:41.14	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:56:59.70	SWS	54.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:57:18.29	SWS	-54.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:57:37.09	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:57:55.76	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:58:14.37	SWS	54.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:58:33.03	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:58:51.88	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:59:10.64	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
11:59:29.66	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
11:59:48.47	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:00:07.08	SWS	54.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:00:25.98	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0

12:00:44.79	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:01:03.57	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:01:22.33	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:01:40.96	SWS	-54.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:01:59.77	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:02:18.44	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:02:37.19	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:02:55.88	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:03:14.57	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:03:20.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
12:03:33.62	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:03:42.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
12:03:52.41	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:04:02.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
12:04:11.05	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:04:16.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
12:04:29.64	SWS	54.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:04:48.53	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:05:07.14	SWS	54.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:05:25.80	SWS	-55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:05:44.40	SWS	54.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:05:58.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
12:06:03.20	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:06:06.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
12:06:22.20	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:06:41.10	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:07:00.20	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:07:19.21	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:07:38.21	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:07:56.98	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:08:13.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:08:13.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:08:13.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:08:14.55	LSH	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
12:08:14.76	SWS	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
12:08:15.14	USH	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
12:08:15.62	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:08:27.41	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 30ms to 50ms.
12:08:29.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:08:31.41	SWS	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
12:08:34.74	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:08:53.50	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:09:12.03	SWS	-54.4	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:09:30.82	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:09:43.86	---	-	-	-	-	*** FL320
12:09:49.65	SWS	-55.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:10:08.44	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:10:27.42	SWS	-55.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:10:46.34	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:11:05.35	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:11:24.25	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:11:43.00	SWS	-55.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:12:01.71	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:12:20.60	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:12:39.44	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:12:58.38	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:13:17.33	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:13:36.12	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:13:54.83	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:14:13.77	SWS	-55.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:14:32.46	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:14:51.00	SWS	-54.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:15:10.02	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:15:28.92	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:15:47.51	SWS	54.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:16:06.45	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:16:25.60	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:16:44.32	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:17:03.23	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0

12:17:22.36	SWS	-55.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:17:41.34	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:18:00.41	SWS	-55.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:18:19.01	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:18:37.90	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:18:47.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
12:18:56.72	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:19:03.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
12:19:15.43	SWS	-55.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:19:22.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
12:19:34.03	SWS	54.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:19:45.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
12:19:52.64	SWS	-54.9	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:19:56.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
12:20:11.45	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:20:24.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
12:20:30.28	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:20:49.31	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:21:08.24	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:21:27.03	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:21:45.74	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:22:04.71	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:22:23.46	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:22:42.18	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:23:01.03	SWS	-55.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:23:19.73	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:23:38.61	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:23:57.31	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:24:15.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:24:15.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:24:15.74	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:24:16.17	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:24:16.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:24:17.21	SWS	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
12:24:17.45	USH	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
12:24:18.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
12:24:22.51	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 100ms.
12:24:24.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:24:26.44	SWS	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
12:24:34.78	SWS	54.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:24:49.62	LSH	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
12:24:53.35	SWS	-54.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:25:12.26	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:25:31.25	SWS	-55.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:25:50.04	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:26:08.79	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:26:27.88	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:26:46.83	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:27:05.63	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:27:24.52	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:27:43.39	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:28:02.14	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:28:21.14	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:28:40.19	SWS	-55.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:28:59.00	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:29:17.82	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:29:36.73	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:29:55.64	SWS	-55.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:30:14.54	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:30:33.64	SWS	-55.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:30:52.15	SWS	54.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:31:10.92	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:31:29.64	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:31:48.65	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:32:07.43	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:32:26.25	SWS	-55.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:32:44.87	SWS	54.7	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:33:03.83	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:33:22.79	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0

12:33:41.77	SWS	-55.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:33:53.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
12:34:00.56	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:34:05.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
12:34:19.46	SWS	-55.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:34:27.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
12:34:38.53	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:34:47.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
12:34:57.48	SWS	-55.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:35:02.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
12:35:16.59	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:35:35.37	SWS	-55.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:35:54.15	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:36:12.85	SWS	-54.8	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:36:31.86	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:36:50.70	SWS	-55.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:37:09.47	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:37:28.27	SWS	-55.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:37:47.30	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:38:05.83	SWS	-54.5	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:38:24.82	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:38:43.69	SWS	-55.3	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:38:57.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:38:57.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:38:57.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:38:59.47	USH	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
12:38:59.59	SWS	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
12:38:59.66	LSH	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
12:39:02.46	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:39:21.31	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:39:40.17	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:39:59.30	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:40:17.88	SWS	54.6	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:40:36.88	SWS	-55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:40:55.57	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:41:14.47	SWS	-55.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:41:33.17	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:41:52.07	SWS	-55.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:42:11.24	SWS	55.0	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:42:30.29	SWS	-55.2	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
12:42:49.30	SWS	55.1	-	-	-	Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
12:43:06.72	SWS	-47.6	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:43:11.99	SWS	-47.5	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
12:43:34.93	---	-	-	-	-	*** Spiral descent
12:45:34.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
12:45:41.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:45:43.21	SWS	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
12:45:45.95	SWS	-	-	50	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
12:45:47.23	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:45:48.77	SWS	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
12:46:36.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
12:46:36.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
12:49:54.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
12:50:10.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
12:50:29.88	SWS	-	-	30	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 30ms.
12:50:32.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:50:33.99	SWS	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
12:50:35.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:50:37.47	USH	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
12:50:38.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:50:39.81	LSH	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
12:54:40.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
12:54:42.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
13:03:40.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:03:40.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:03:40.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:03:42.12	SWS	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
13:03:42.49	LSH	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
13:03:42.64	USH	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.

```

13:05:47.26 --- - - - - *** FL150
13:06:09.48 SWS - - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
13:07:56.03 SWS -6.0 - - - - Telescope sent to -55.000
13:08:04.64 SWS -55.0 - - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
13:08:23.51 SWS 55.0 - - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
13:08:42.62 SWS -55.0 - - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
13:09:01.32 SWS 55.0 - - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
13:09:02.80 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:09:04.38 SWS - - 303 0 Manual scene recording started.
13:09:09.47 SWS - - 100 - VIS int.time changed from 30ms to 100ms.
13:09:16.04 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:09:17.51 SWS - - 303 0 Manual scene recording started.
13:09:20.29 SWS -55.1 - - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
13:09:39.23 SWS 55.0 - - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
13:09:58.10 SWS -55.1 - - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
13:10:16.78 SWS 55.0 - - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
13:10:35.71 SWS -55.1 - - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
13:10:54.32 SWS 54.8 - - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
13:11:13.15 SWS -55.1 - - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
13:11:32.12 SWS 55.0 - - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
13:11:50.91 SWS -55.1 - - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
13:12:09.88 SWS 55.0 - - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
13:12:28.88 SWS -55.0 - - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
13:12:47.69 SWS 55.0 - - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
13:13:06.77 SWS -55.0 - - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
13:13:25.72 SWS 55.0 - - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
13:13:44.87 SWS -55.0 - - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
13:14:03.94 SWS 55.0 - - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
13:14:22.81 SWS -55.0 - - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
13:14:41.78 SWS 55.0 - - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
13:15:00.44 SWS -55.1 - - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
13:15:19.48 SWS 55.0 - - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
13:15:38.46 SWS -55.1 - - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
13:15:57.39 SWS 55.0 - - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
13:16:16.33 SWS -55.1 - - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
13:16:35.37 SWS 55.0 - - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
13:16:54.31 SWS -55.1 - - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
13:17:13.12 SWS 55.0 - - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
13:17:31.71 SWS -54.7 - - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
13:17:50.79 SWS 55.0 - - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
13:18:09.89 SWS -55.1 - - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
13:18:28.76 SWS 55.0 - - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
13:18:47.74 SWS -55.0 - - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to 55.0
13:19:06.67 SWS 55.0 - - - - Telescope at scan limit - going to -55.0
13:19:15.67 SWS 3.3 - - - - Telescope stopped.
13:19:19.62 SWS 3.3 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
13:19:22.22 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:19:22.29 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:19:22.33 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:19:23.80 SWS - - 303 0 Manual scene recording started.
13:19:24.24 LSH - - 303 0 Manual scene recording started.
13:19:24.53 USH - - 303 0 Manual scene recording started.
13:19:31.20 SWS - 250 - - Sample period changed from 100ms to 250ms.
13:19:33.61 USH - 250 - - Sample period changed from 100ms to 250ms.
13:19:36.23 LSH - 250 - - Sample period changed from 100ms to 250ms.
13:19:52.42 --- - - - - ***
13:20:56.91 --- - - - - *** The int time values "303 0" above are
cosmetic and do not represent reality.
13:21:16.80 --- - - - - *** This is whatyou get for meddling with
software pre-flight!
13:23:29.51 SWS - - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
13:25:56.03 SWS - - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
13:27:12.45 SWS - - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
13:27:46.64 SWS - - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
13:27:54.33 SWS - - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
13:28:27.85 SWS - - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
13:28:56.42 SWS - - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
13:29:00.81 SWS - - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
13:29:40.47 SWS - - - - Warning: Clipping may be occurring.

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13:30:00.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
13:30:21.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
13:30:31.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
13:30:34.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
13:31:30.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
13:31:39.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
13:31:47.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
13:32:22.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
13:32:36.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
13:32:45.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
13:33:00.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
13:38:09.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:38:09.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:38:09.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:38:11.42	SWS	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
13:38:11.85	LSH	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
13:38:12.03	USH	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
13:38:19.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:38:20.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:38:20.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:38:21.46	USH	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
13:38:21.66	LSH	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
13:38:21.89	SWS	-	-	303	0	Manual scene recording started.
13:38:27.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:38:29.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:38:31.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:38:43.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Instrument closed.
13:38:47.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Instrument closed.
13:38:51.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Instrument closed.
13:39:37.78	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 128.779
13:39:39.58	SWS	128.8	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:39:43.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Telescope disabled.
13:39:47.41	---	-	-	-	-	*** SHUTTING DOWN...
13:39:47.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Telescope motor control quit.